

Transport Processes in Thermo-cells

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Domain of validity of thermodynamics of irreversible processes has been examined experimentally in the case of transport processes in thermo-cells. Earlier theory of thermo-cells has been revised to suit the experiments described. The data obtained have also been used to study the effect of concentration, temperature, and the nature of other ion on the heat and entropy of transport.

Many attempts¹⁻⁴ have been made to increase the domain of applicability of thermodynamics of irreversible processes to the non-linear region. Unfortunately, scant information is available from experiments about the range of applicability of non-equilibrium thermodynamics. This communication deals with an attempt in this direction in the case of thermo-cells. Our experiments, where the two halves of the thermo-cell are kept at two temperatures, do not correspond to the conventional theory of thermo-cells⁵ in which the system is assumed to be a continuous one. Therefore, the earlier theory of thermo-cells⁵ has been modified to suit our experiments. Experiments have been described to examine the range of validity of the theory. The opportunity has been utilised to study the effect of temperature, concentration, and the effect of other ion on final thermo-electric power which is related to heat and entropy of transport.

Theoretical

The experimental set up, which is different from that of earlier workers⁶, essentially consists of two half cells kept in two thermostats, maintained at two different temperatures and connected by means of a common tube passing through the walls of the thermostats. The important points in the present experimental set-up are:

- (1) The two subsystems, which we will refer as (I) and (II) in this communication, are individually open systems.
- (2) The total system (I) + (II) is a closed system and can exchange energy with only the exterior and not the matter.

The thermo-cell studied can be represented in the following manner.

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The total E.M.F. of such a cell would be the sum of the potential difference of single electrode potentials of Ag-AgCl/MCl electrode at temperatures T and $(T + \Delta T)$ and the potential difference due to the concentration gradient established by setting of the Soret equilibrium plus the E.M.F. due to contact potential at the electrode-metal interface and the E.M.F. due to homogeneous thermoelectric power of the metallic conductor. We can safely neglect the terms due to contact potential difference and homogeneous thermo-electric power because of their small magnitudes. Thus

$$(\Delta\varphi)_{\text{total}} = (\Delta\varphi)_{\text{rev.}} + (\Delta\varphi)_{\text{sol.}}$$

where $(\Delta\varphi)_{\text{rev.}}$ represents the potential difference due to the difference in the single electrode potentials at different temperatures and $(\Delta\varphi)_{\text{sol.}}$ represents what may be called thermal diffusion potential. We now proceed to evaluate both these terms one by one.

Consider an electrolyte solution having n species in a temperature gradient:

$$\begin{array}{c} | \text{ Solution} | \\ T \qquad \qquad T + \Delta T \end{array}$$

The temperature gradient gives rise to a concentration gradient and an electrical potential gradient. Thus there would be interaction among the flows of matter, heat, and electricity. Only two out of these three flows are, however, independent. The flow of electricity occurs due to the flow of ions carrying different charges, *i.e.*, the flow of electricity is associated with the flow of matter.

The Fundamental Equations.—As we have no chemical reaction among the components $k = 1, 2, \dots, n$ of the solution and the total system is closed one, the law of conservation of mass is expressed by

$$dM_k^I + dM_k^{II} = 0 \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

Here I and II denote the two subsystems.

The change in energy, dU^I , may be split into an external part deU^I , the energy exchanged with the surroundings, and diU^I , the energy exchanged with the vessel II. A similar splitting holds for the subsystem II. We have therefore.

$$dU^I = deU^I + diU^I; \quad dU^{II} = deU^{II} + diU^{II} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

Conservation of energy is given by the expression

$$diU^I + diU^{II} = 0 \quad \dots \quad (4)$$

For the subsystems I and II, the Gibbs equation can be written as

$$T^I dS^I = dU^I + P^I dV^I - \sum_{k=1}^n \tilde{\mu}_k^I dM_k^I \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

$$T^{II} dS^{II} = dU^{II} + P^{II} dV^{II} - \sum_{k=1}^n \tilde{\mu}_k^{II} dM_k^{II} \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

The electro-chemical potential $\tilde{\mu}_k$ is related to the chemical potential μ_k by the equation

$$\tilde{\mu}_k = \mu_k + e_k \varphi \quad \dots \quad (7)$$

where e_k is the specific electric charge of the component k and φ is the electrical potential. For the change of entropy of the total system we have, with the help of equations (2) and (4):

$$dS = dS^I + dS^{II} \\ = \frac{deU^I + P^I dV^I}{T^I} + \frac{deU^{II} + P^{II} dV^{II}}{T^{II}} + diU^I \cdot \frac{\Delta T}{T^I} + \sum_{k=1}^n \Delta \left(\frac{\bar{\mu}_k}{T} \right) dM_k^I \quad (8)$$

This expression for the change of entropy can be split into two parts: one giving the entropy received from the surroundings:

$$deS = \frac{deU^I + P^I dV^I}{T^I} + \frac{deU^{II} + P^{II} dV^{II}}{T^{II}} \quad \dots \quad (9)$$

the other giving the internal production of entropy which results from the action of irreversible processes inside the system:

$$diS = diU^I \cdot \frac{\Delta T}{T^I} + \sum_{k=1}^n \Delta \left(\frac{\bar{\mu}_k}{T} \right) dM_k^I \quad \dots \quad (10)$$

Thus production of entropy per unit of time is given by

$$\sigma = \frac{diS}{dt} = \frac{diU^I}{dt} \cdot \frac{\Delta T}{T^I} + \sum_{k=1}^n \Delta \left(\frac{\bar{\mu}_k}{T} \right) \frac{dM_k^I}{dt} \quad \dots \quad (11)$$

Now with the help of the above equation, the flow of energy J_u and the flow of matter J_k and the corresponding forces X_u and X_k can be written as

$$J_u = - \frac{diU^I}{dt} = \frac{diU^{II}}{dt} \quad \dots \quad (12)$$

$$J_k = - \frac{dM_k^I}{dt} = \frac{dM_k^{II}}{dt} \quad \dots \quad (13)$$

$$X_u = - \frac{\Delta T}{T^I} \quad \dots \quad (14)$$

$$X_k = - \Delta \left(\frac{\bar{\mu}_k}{T} \right) = - \Delta \left(\frac{\mu_k}{T} \right) - e_k \Delta \left(\frac{\varphi}{T} \right) \quad \dots \quad (15)$$

Now after having chosen the fluxes J_u and J_k and the corresponding forces X_u and X_k , we can write the linear phenomenological relation as

$$J_i = \sum_{k=1}^n L_{ik} X_k + L_{iu} X_u \quad \dots \quad (16)$$

$$J_u = \sum_{k=1}^n L_{uk} X_k + L_{uu} X_u \quad \dots \quad (17)$$

The Energies of Transfer.—Introducing the quantities U_k^* as defined by de Groot⁷

$$L_{iu} = \sum_{k=1}^n L_{ik} U_k^* \quad \dots \quad (18)$$

the equation (16) is written as

$$J_i = \sum_{k=1}^n L_{ik} (X_k + U_k^* + X_u) \quad \dots \quad (19)$$

With the help of equations (19), (17), and Onsager's reciprocal relations, we get

$$J_u = \sum_{i=1}^n U_i^* J_i + (L_{uu} - \sum_{i,k=1}^n L_{ik} U_i^* U_k^*) X_u \quad \dots \quad (20)$$

Steady State.—Steady state is defined as the situation where all diffusion flows vanish, but an energy flow still exists:

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} J_i = 0 \\ J_u \neq 0 \end{array} \right\} \quad (i = 1, 2, \dots, n) \quad \dots \quad (21)$$

From equation (21) we have for the steady state after substituting the values of X_k and X_u :

$$-\Delta \left(\frac{\mu_k}{T} \right) - e_k \Delta \left(\frac{\varphi}{T} \right) - U_k^* \frac{\Delta T}{T^2} = 0 \quad \dots \quad (22)$$

But we know that

$$\Delta \left(\frac{\mu_k}{T} \right) = -h_k \frac{\Delta T}{T^2} + v_k \frac{\Delta P}{T} + \frac{\delta \mu_k}{\delta m} \cdot \frac{\Delta m}{T} \quad \dots \quad (23)$$

where h_k and v_k are the partial specific enthalpy and volume respectively and m is the molality. It should be noted here that for a completely dissociated uni-univalent electrolyte

$$m = m_1 = m_2 \quad \dots \quad (24)$$

where m_1 and m_2 are the ionic molalities of the ions produced by dissociation of one mole of the electrolyte.

With the help of equations (22) and (23) and assuming mechanical equilibrium, i.e., $\Delta P = 0$, we can write

$$e_k \Delta \left(\frac{\varphi}{T} \right) + \frac{\delta \mu_k}{\delta m} \cdot \frac{\Delta m}{T} + Q_k^* \frac{\Delta T}{T^2} = 0 \quad \dots \quad (25)$$

where Q_k^* is known as the heat of transport of the component k and is given by

$$Q_k^* = U_k^* - h_k \quad \dots \quad (26)$$

We also know that

$$e_k = Z_k \cdot F \quad \dots \quad (27)$$

where Z_k is the valency of the component k and F is the Faraday. Assuming T in $\Delta(\varphi/T)$ to be mean temperature, we can write equation (25) as

7. "Thermodynamics of Irreversible Processes", North Holland Publishing Co., Amsterdam, 1952.

$$Z_k F \cdot \Delta \varphi + \frac{\delta \mu_k}{\delta m} \cdot \Delta m + Q_k^* \cdot \frac{\Delta T}{T} = 0 \quad \dots \quad (28)$$

which is the final expression applicable to the steady state.

Non-stationary Situations.—The usual approximation, which is made in the theory of non-stationary state, is

$$I = \sum_{k=1}^n e_k J_k = 0 \quad \dots \quad (29)$$

i.e., the total electrical current is supposed to be negligible. The solvent is supposed to be neutral. The phenomenological coefficients, L_{ik} , are known⁷ to be related to the transport numbers t_k in the following manner:

$$t_k = \frac{e_k \sum_{i,k} L_{ki} e_i}{\sum_{i,k} L_{ik} e_i e_k} \quad \dots \quad (30)$$

With the help of equations (27), (29), (30), and (23) and remembering that there is mechanical equilibrium in our system, we can write

$$\Delta \varphi = - \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{t_k}{Z_k F} \frac{\delta \mu_k}{\delta m} \cdot \Delta m - \sum_{k=1}^n \frac{t_k}{Z_k F} \cdot Q_k^* \cdot \frac{\Delta T}{T} \quad \dots \quad (31)$$

Equation (31) holds for an arbitrary moment and can be used for the evaluation of $(\Delta \varphi)_{\text{sol}}$.

Using molality m as variable, describing the composition of a single binary electrolyte, we can write equation (31) as

$$- F \left(\frac{\Delta \varphi}{\Delta T} \right)_{\text{sol}} = \left(\frac{t_1}{Z_1} \mu'_1 + \frac{t_2}{Z_2} \mu'_2 \right) \frac{\Delta m}{\Delta T} + \frac{t_1}{Z_1} \frac{Q_1^*}{T} + \frac{t_2}{Z_2} \frac{Q_2^*}{T} \quad \dots \quad (32)$$

and equation (25) as

$$Z_1 F \cdot \Delta \varphi + \mu'_1 \Delta m + \frac{Q_1^*}{T} \Delta T = 0 \quad \dots \quad (33)$$

$$Z_2 F \Delta \varphi + \mu'_2 \Delta m + \frac{Q_2^*}{T} \Delta T = 0 \quad \dots \quad (34)$$

where $\delta \mu_i / \delta m$ has been put equal to μ'_i and the subscripts 1 and 2 refer to cation and anion respectively. Equations (33) and (34) can be solved to provide the stationary Soret effect:

$$\left(\frac{\Delta m}{\Delta T} \right)_{\text{stat.}} = - \frac{\nu_1 Q_1^* + \nu_2 Q_2^*}{\mu' T} \quad \dots \quad (35)$$

where ν_i is the number of ions of the species i obtained by the dissociation of one molecule of the electrolyte and

$$\mu = \nu_1 \mu_1 + \nu_2 \mu_2 \quad \dots \quad (36)$$

Evaluation of $(\Delta\varphi)_{rev}$.—Considering two electrodes in the solution of its ions at temperatures T and $T + \Delta T$ and by applying the conditions of local equilibrium, we get

$$\begin{aligned} Z_i F \cdot (\Delta\varphi)_{rev} &= (\mu_{iA} - \mu_i) - [(\mu_{iA} + d\mu_{iA}) - (\mu_i + d\mu_i)] \\ &= - \frac{\delta\mu_{iA}}{\delta T} \cdot \Delta T + \frac{\delta\mu_i}{\delta T} \Delta T + \frac{\delta\mu_i}{\delta m} \Delta m + \dots \quad \dots \quad (37) \end{aligned}$$

where the subscripts iA and i represent the species i in the electrode and in the solution respectively. Equation (37) can otherwise be written as

$$Z_i F \cdot \left(\frac{\Delta\varphi}{\Delta T} \right)_{rev} = S_{iA} - S_i + \mu'_i \frac{\Delta m}{\Delta T} \quad \dots \quad (38)$$

S represents the entropy. Since entropy S_m of the metal is the sum of the entropies of ions S_{iA} and electrons $(S_{el})_A$, we have

$$S_m = S_{iA} + Z_i \cdot (S_{el})_A \quad \dots \quad (39)$$

We also know that

$$S_i = S_i^\circ - R \ln m_i r_i - RT \frac{\delta \ln r_i}{\delta T} \quad \dots \quad (40)$$

S_i° is the standard partial molar entropy of the ion i in the solution. Now with the help of equations (39) and (40), equation (38) reads as

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{\Delta\varphi}{\Delta T} \right)_{rev} &= \frac{S_m}{Z_i F} - \frac{S_i^\circ}{Z_i F} \times \frac{R}{Z_i F} \ln m_i r_i + \frac{RT}{Z_i F} \frac{\delta \ln r_i}{\delta T} \\ &\quad - \frac{(S_{el})_A}{F} + \frac{\mu'_i}{Z_i F} \frac{\Delta m}{\Delta T} \quad \dots \quad (41) \end{aligned}$$

Total Value of $(\Delta\varphi/\Delta T)$.—The total value can be obtained by combining equations (41) and (32).

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{\Delta\varphi}{\Delta T} \right) &= \frac{S_m}{Z_i F} - \frac{S_i^\circ}{Z_i F} + \frac{R}{Z_i F} \ln m_i r_i + \frac{RT}{Z_i F} \frac{\delta \ln r_i}{\delta T} - \frac{(S_{el})_A}{F} + \\ &\quad \left(\frac{\mu'_i}{Z_i F} - \frac{t_1}{Z_i} \mu'_i - \frac{t_2}{Z_i F} \mu'_2 \right) \frac{\Delta m}{\Delta T} \\ &\quad - \left(\frac{t_1}{Z_i F} \frac{Q_1^*}{T} + \frac{t_2}{Z_2 F} \frac{Q_2^*}{T} \right) \quad \dots \quad (42) \end{aligned}$$

It is easy to show that

$$\frac{\mu'_i}{Z_i F} - \frac{t_1}{Z_i F} \mu'_i - \frac{t_2}{Z_i F} \mu'_2 = \pm \frac{(1-t_1)}{\nu_1 \nu_2 q F} \mu' \quad \dots \quad (43)$$

where q is the positive rational number. Positive sign holds if it is a cation and negative sign holds if it is an anion. Now equation (42) reads as

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{\Delta\varphi}{\Delta T} \right) &= \pm \frac{(1-t_1)}{\nu_1 \nu_2 q F} \mu' \frac{\Delta m}{\Delta T} + \frac{R}{Z_i F} \ln m_i + \frac{S_m}{Z_i F} - \frac{(S_{el})_A}{F} + \frac{R}{Z_i F} \left(\ln r_i + T \frac{\delta \ln r_i}{\delta T} \right) \\ &\quad - \frac{S_i^\circ}{Z_i F} - \frac{1}{F T} \left(\frac{t_1}{Z_i} Q_1^* + \frac{t_2}{Z_2} Q_2^* \right) \quad \dots \quad (44) \end{aligned}$$

Initial Thermo-electric Power.—At time $t = 0$, $\Delta m / \Delta T = 0$; hence from equation (44) we have

$$\left(\frac{\Delta \varphi}{\Delta T}\right)_{t=0} = \frac{R}{Z_i F} \ln m_i r_i + \frac{RT}{Z_i F} \cdot \frac{\delta \ln r_i}{\delta T} + \frac{S_m}{Z_i F} + \frac{S_i^0}{Z_i F} - \frac{(S_{el})_A}{F} - \frac{1}{F T} \left(\frac{t_1}{Z_1} Q_1^* + \frac{t_2}{Z_2} Q_2^* \right) \quad \dots \quad (45)$$

Equation (45) provides the value of initial thermo-electric power of the thermo-cell.

Final Thermo-electric Power.—The value of final thermo-electric power can be obtained by combining equations (44) and (35). Thus we get

$$\left(\frac{\Delta \varphi}{\Delta T}\right)_{t=\infty} = \frac{R}{Z_i F} \ln m_i r_i + \frac{RT}{Z_i F} \frac{\delta \ln r_i}{\delta T} + \frac{S_m}{Z_i F} - \frac{S_i^0}{Z_i F} - \frac{(S_{el})_A}{F} - \frac{1}{F T} Q_i^* \quad (46)$$

For all practical purposes $(S_{el})_A / F$ term can be omitted from the expressions for the initial and final thermo-electric powers in view of its negligible magnitudes.

EXPERIMENTAL

Sodium and potassium chloride, used in the present study were of AnalaR grade obtained from M/s B. D. H., London. Conductivity water, prepared by redistilling distilled water over alkaline permanganate, was used for preparing the solutions.

Silver-silver chloride electrodes used in the present study were prepared by the method of Carmody⁶. The electrodes, thus prepared, though brownish in colour, had asymmetry potential of only 10 to 100 microvolts and were stable for about one month.

Asymmetry Potential of the Electrodes.—The reversibility of the electrodes was tested by measuring the E.M.F. of the cell:

where the two electrodes were kept at the same temperature. The asymmetry potential of the electrodes was always less than 100 microvolts. The asymmetry of the electrodes was noticed to show a tendency to increase if the electrodes were not given sufficient rest between two runs. It was found that a rest of roughly 24 hours, during which the electrodes were kept in conductivity water, was sufficient to restore the original asymmetry potential of the electrodes. The electrodes, when not in use, were always kept in short circuited condition in conductivity water. Further, the conductivity water, in which the electrodes were stored, was changed from time to time. If the medium between the electrodes was shaken, the asymmetry potential was also found to change, but as soon as the steady conditions prevailed, it assumed the normal value. The asymmetry potential was

greatly affected if the two electrodes were prepared separately. These observations regarding the asymmetry of the electrodes are partly in agreement with those of Chapman and Tyrrell⁹.

Design of the Thermo-cell.—The thermo-cell consisted of essentially three parts—A, B, and C. The part A was a glass tube with two B-10 standard male joints at the end and a stop-cock with a long stem in the middle. The parts B and C consisted of two pyrex test tubes with straight side tubes, each having one B-10 female joint at the end. The part A of the thermo-cell was permanently fixed between the two thermostat tanks. Two holes were drawn in one of the walls of both the thermostat tanks in which were fitted two rubber corks through which passed the tube of the part A. The stop-cock D' was in between the two thermostat tanks and was carefully covered with cotton. The stem of the stop-cock was quite long so that it may be opened conveniently. The experimental set up is shown schematically in Fig. 1.

FIG. 1. Design of the thermo-cell.

Measurement of Potential Difference and Experimental Procedures.—Potential differences were measured by a Pye precision vernier potentiometer with the help of a Cambridge galvanometer. For standardisation a Cambridge standard normal cadmium cell was used. 28 S. W. Copper-constantan thermocouples were used for measuring the temperatures. The thermo-cell was first thoroughly cleansed and rinsed with the solution to be investigated. Then the parts B and C of the thermo-cell were connected with the part A and the whole was firmly clamped. The solution of the electrolyte was then filled in the cell cautiously to avoid any air bubble left in the tube of the part A. The thermostats were filled with water in such a way that the level of the solution in the thermo-cell was well below the level of the water in the thermostats. The stop-cock was then closed and the thermostats were set at required temperatures. Electrodes were then introduced in the tubes B and C and were kept for half an hour to enable the electrodes to attain the temperature of the solution in the cell. The stop-cock D' was then opened and the E.M.F. was recorded instantaneously. This gives the value of $(\Delta\varphi)_{t=0}$. The E.M.F. was noted continuously till the steady value was attained. This gives the value of $(\Delta\varphi)_{t=\infty}$. Reproducibility of the result was always within ± 3 to 4%.

Discussion of Errors.—We shall mainly try to assess the uncertainty in the values of $(\Delta\varphi/\Delta T)$.

(a). The maximum error in the measurement of $\Delta\varphi$ was one microvolt. Since $(\Delta\varphi)$ was fairly large, the error introduced on this account was always below 0.2%.

(b). The maximum uncertainty in the temperature of one thermostat was $\pm 0.05^\circ$. Hence the maximum uncertainty in the measurement of ΔT was $\pm 0.1^\circ$.

Certain unavoidable errors were introduced on account of the set-up of the experiment. The construction of the electrodes is shown in Fig. 2. The electrode was of the type (a). A stout platinum wire was fused in a glass tube. The electrical contact was made through the mercury. The platinum wire was coated with silver and later on with AgCl.

FIG. 2. Construction of the electrode.

Since silver chloride is a bad conductor of heat, it is doubtful whether the temperature of the platinum electrode will correspond to the temperature of the solution in a particular half cell. This difficulty becomes all the more serious since the connecting wires are at room temperature and the mercury may also be expected to acquire the temperature of the air above it. It seems therefore that a temperature gradient exists inside the electrode system itself. If the heat passing out through mercury is $d\theta$, the temperature gradient would roughly be $d\theta/\kappa A$ where κ is the overall thermal conductivity and A is the area. We cannot make a quantitative estimate of the temperature gradient, but we can say with a reasonable confidence that such a gradient would exist.

Error due to Convection Bends.—While discussing the theory, it has been assumed that the diffusion flows exist along the axis of X only. This implies that both the electrodes should be horizontal in line with the tube of the part A of the thermo-cell. Gradients along the axes of Y and Z would also become important if the electrodes are not horizontal in line with the tube A. It should be mentioned here that the reproducible values were obtained only when the electrodes were kept horizontally in line with the tube A.

DISCUSSION

A complete test of the theory of thermo-cells developed in this communication is difficult since the values of the heat of transport, ionic activity coefficients, and their temperature dependence are not known. A partial test of the theory is, however, possible. Looking into equation (46) for final thermo-electric power, it becomes obvious that for the solution of the same ionic strength maintained at the same mean temperature, $\Delta\varphi$ should be directly proportional to ΔT , the temperature difference between the two thermostats, since quantities on the right hand side of equation (48) are more or less constants. Broadly speaking, the proportionality would break at the point when the non-equilibrium thermodynamic theory of thermo-cell would fail. The value of ΔT , at which the departure from linearity occurs, would correspond to the upper limit of the validity of the theory of thermo-cell outlined herein. The evaluation of the upper limit was made from the study of the cell:

The values of $\Delta\varphi$ for 0.1M-KCl at mean temperature of 50° are plotted against ΔT in Fig. 3. It can be seen that the linearity does not break up to $\Delta T = 25^\circ$. This broadly sets the upper limit of the domain of validity of thermodynamics of irreversible processes in thermo-cells.

FIG. 3. Variation of $\Delta\varphi$ with ΔT .

To ascertain how far these data can supply useful information about the heat of transfer and entropy of transfer, the following equations may be considered:

When $i = 2 =$ chloride ion and $Z_i = -1$, equation (46) reads as

$$\epsilon_\infty = \left(\frac{\Delta\varphi}{\Delta T}\right)_{T=\infty} = -\frac{R}{F} \ln m_2 r_2 - \frac{RT}{F} \frac{\delta \ln r_2}{\delta T} - \frac{1}{F} (S_m - S_2^\circ + S_{el}) + \frac{1}{F} \cdot S_2^\circ \quad (47)$$

For a fixed concentration this reduces to

$$\epsilon_\infty = A - \frac{R}{F} \ln r_2 - \frac{RT}{F} \frac{\delta \ln r_2}{\delta T} + \frac{1}{F} S_2^\circ \quad \dots \quad (48)$$

where

$$A = -\frac{R}{F} \ln m_2 - \frac{1}{F} (S_m - S^\circ + S_{el}) \quad \dots \quad (49)$$

FIG. 4. Variation of F.T.P. with temp. for 0.06M-KCl.

FIG. 5. Variation of F.T.P. with temp. for 0.02M-NaCl.

For a small temperature range S_m , S_2° , and S_{el} are constants and hence S_2° would vary with temperature in the same fashion as ϵ_∞ does. Figs. 4 and 5 show that S_2° decreases with the temperature for 0.06M-KCl and 0.02M-NaCl solutions. For

$$\frac{d\epsilon_\infty}{dT} = -\frac{ZR}{F} \frac{\delta \ln r_2}{\delta T} - \frac{RT}{F} \cdot \frac{\delta^2 \ln r_2}{\delta T^2} + \frac{1}{F} \cdot \frac{dS_2^\circ}{dT} \quad \dots \quad (50)$$

and since $\frac{\delta \ln r_2}{\delta T}$ and $\frac{\delta^2 \ln r_2}{\delta T^2}$ are of very small magnitudes

$$\frac{d\epsilon_{\infty}}{dT} \approx \frac{dS_a^{\infty}}{dT} \tag{51}$$

Similarly variation of ϵ_{∞} with concentration will give the approximate nature of the variation of heat of transport on concentration. Such a plot has been shown in Fig. 6 for sodium chloride.

FIG. 6 variation of F.T.P. with NaCl conc.

From equation (46) it follows that if Q_2^* has the same value when KCl and NaCl solutions of same molar concentrations are being used in the cell, the final thermo-electric power should be the same in all such cells, provided that the ionic activity coefficients are the same. The latter condition should be expected to be satisfied in very dilute solutions obeying the Debye-Hückel theory. In other words, it means that if the final thermo-electric powers of the thermo-cells, reversible with respect to cation or anion, having similar electrolytes of identical concentrations are the same, the heat of transport of the anion or the cation would be independent of the nature of the other ion. The final thermo-electric power of the cells:

FIG. 7. Variation of F.T.P. with nature of cation.

● denotes NaCl
⊙ " KCl

is plotted in Fig. 7. It is found that these agree within $\pm 4\%$. This goes to prove that the heat of transport of chloride ion is independent of the nature of the cation. Similar results have been obtained by Rastogi *et al.*¹⁰ for silver ions.

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